

NOTES

Syntheses of New Oxovanadium(IV) Complexes with Tridentate Dibasic Schiff bases Derived from Salicylaldehyde, Substituted Salicylaldehyde and Orthohydroxybenzylamine

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Manuscript received 2 November 1977, revised 5 May 1978,

accepted 10 May 1978

THE tridentate dibasic ligands yield metal complexes which usually show novel spectral, magnetic and structural properties^{1,2}. Recently there has been considerable interest on the syntheses and magnetic properties of oxovanadium(IV) and copper(II) complexes of tridentate dibasic Schiff bases derived from salicylaldehyde or substituted salicylaldehyde and orthoaminophenol or orthoaminothiophenol³⁻⁵. In this preliminary communication the syntheses of a few new oxovanadium(IV) complexes of tridentate dibasic Schiff bases (I) derived from salicylaldehyde or substituted salicylaldehyde and orthohydroxybenzylamine are reported. Only the dioxouranium(VI) complexes of I have recently been described⁶.

I

Method of preparation of the complexes :

A solution of the appropriate Schiff base (0.005M) was prepared by refluxing salicylaldehyde or substituted salicylaldehyde (0.005 M) in 50 ml of methanol. To this solution a methanolic solution of freshly prepared vanadyl acetate (0.005 M in 20 ml) was added slowly with stirring. The mixture was refluxed for 2 hrs. with stirring. The separated precipitates were filtered, washed with methanol and dried under vacuum. The characterisation data of the complexes are given in Table 1.

The analytical data indicate metal : ligand ratio, 1 : 1 for all the complexes. The infrared spectra of the complexes show the absence of $\nu(\text{OH})$ stretch. This is indicative of coordination of phenolic oxygens to VO(IV) and the dibasic character of these Schiff bases. The $\nu(\text{V}=\text{O})$ stretch of the complexes is given in Table 1 and this occurs in the range 900-910 cm^{-1} which is in the usual range observed for the majority of oxovanadium(IV) complexes⁷. The complexes are insoluble in common solvents and decompose or melt above 250°. The ligands I behave as tridentate dibasic ligands and this requires that these oxovanadium(IV) complexes will be dimeric or polymeric in order to achieve the normal penta-coordination. The insolubility of the complexes prevented the molecular weight determination of the complexes. The magnetic moments of the complexes were determined at room temperature by the Gouy method using $\text{Hg}[\text{Co}(\text{NCS})_4]$ as the standard. The complexes exhibit the room temperature magnetic moments in the range 1.1-1.2 B.M. which is significantly lower than the spin-only value of 1.73 B.M. expected for magnetically dilute oxovanadium(IV) complexes ($S=\frac{3}{2}$). The low magnetic moment in these complexes indicates the

TABLE 1—THE ANALYTICAL, MAGNETIC MOMENT AND $\text{V}=\text{O}$ FREQUENCY DATA OF OXOVANADIUM(IV) COMPLEXES^a

Complex		%V	%N	μ_{eff} B.M.	$\nu(\text{V}=\text{O})^b$ cm^{-1}
VO(sal-o-hydroxybenzylamine)	Found :	17.1	4.4	1.11	910
	Calcd :	17.47	4.79		
VO(5-chlorosal-o-hydroxybenzylamine)	Found :	14.9	4.2	1.19	905
	Calcd :	15.63	4.29		
VO(5-bromosal-o-hydroxybenzylamine)	Found :	13.4	3.9	1.18	910
	Calcd :	13.75	3.77		
VO(3, 5-dichlorosal-o-hydroxybenzylamine)	Found :	14.1	3.5	1.11	910
	Calcd :	14.13	3.88		
VO(4-methoxysal-o-hydroxybenzylamine)	Found :	15.4	4.1	1.23	900
	Calcd :	14.84	4.35		
VO(hydrox-o-hydroxybenzylamine)	Found :	14.5	3.8	1.10	910
	Calcd :	14.91	4.09		

(a) Abbreviations : sal=salicylaldehyde, 5-chlorosal=5-chlorosalicylaldehyde, 5-bromosal=5-bromosalicylaldehyde, 3, 5-dichlorosal=3, 5-dichlorosalicylaldehyde, 4-methoxysal=4-methoxysalicylaldehyde and hydrox=2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde.

(b) The infrared spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer Model 237 infrared spectrophotometer in KBr pellets.

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spin-spin coupling in the interacting vanadium atoms and the exchange interaction is of the antiferromagnetic type with singlet ground state^{2,3}.

The low temperature magnetic and electron spin resonance studies of the complexes are progressing and details will be reported in due course. The corresponding oxomolybdenum(V), oxotungsten(V) and copper(II) complexes are also being studied in order to compare the magnetic exchange behaviour of these $S = \frac{1}{2}$ systems. The syntheses of coordination complexes of various other transition and non-transition metal ions with I are being carried out.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to the Department of Atomic Energy (Government of India) and faculty research fund of Regional Engineering College, Kurukshetra for financial support of this research. They thank Dr. S. Banerjee for experimental assistance.

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Dissociation Constants of 1, 10-Phenanthroline and its Iron(II) Complex in Ethanol and Water Mixtures

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Manuscript received 28 September 1977, revised 14 February
1978, accepted 26 April 1978

In order to explore the role of the solvents on the dissociation constants of the complexes, we studied the dissociation constants of the following 'iso-electric' equilibria in ethanol+water mixtures. (Containing 8-87 wt% of ethanol)

The thermodynamics of reaction (1) have been reported. We report in this communication the equilibrium constants for reactions (2) and (3) in ethanol+water mixtures.

Methods and Materials

The purification of the solvent, the preparation of ferrous-ammonium-sulphate and 1, 10-phenanthroline solutions, the determination of the weight percentages of the organic solvents in the mixed solvents and their dielectric constants were done in the way described before¹⁻³.

The chemicals used were of G.R. grade. Double-distilled water was used for preparing the solutions.

The organic solvent I has been found to have little effect on the absorption maximum of ferroin which is 510 nm. Under our experimental conditions, FePh_3^{2+} has been assumed to be the sole species formed without any FePh^{2+} and FePh_3^{2+} .

The molar absorptivities ϵ 's of ferroin were determined at 500, 510 and 520 nms from the measurement of absorbances of solutions containing more than 10 fold excess of ligand to known amounts of ferrous ion where complete conversion of Fe^{2+} to FePh_3^{2+} took place.

For the determination of stability constants of ferroin in mixed solvents, absorbances of solutions containing different amounts of Fe^{2+} ion and 1, 10-phenanthroline (Concn. range $8-20 \times 10^{-6} M$) were measured at 500, 510 and 520 nms. The pHs ranged from 2.60-3.80.

For the calculation of equilibrium constants for the reactions (2) and (3), the average values of the complex obtained from absorbance measurements and ϵ values at three wavelengths were taken.

Spectrophotometric readings were taken with a Beckman DU Spectrophotometer maintained at 25°. The pH-meter readings were taken with a Cambridge-bench type battery operated pH-meter.

Results

In mixed solvents, the activity coefficients change due to

(i) Salt effect (f_i), (ii) Medium effect (f_m). Salt effect may be eliminated by working in very dilute solutions so that

$f_i \rightarrow 1$, i.e. $f_{\text{Fe}^{2+}} = f_{\text{FePh}_3^{2+}}$ and $f_{\text{H}^+} = f_{\text{PhH}^+}$. This enables us to get an idea regarding 'medium effect' with which we are concerned in our studies in mixed solvents. Furthermore, addition of inert electrolyte or increase in the concentrations of reactions would lead to further complications due to

- (a) ion-association,
- (b) Solute-solvent interactions and preferential solvation of ions in mixed solvents.